

The FAIR Cookbook

for **doers**, **users**, and **contributors**

explore the
FAIR Cookbook

faircookbook.elixir-europe.org

explore

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adopt

assess your
FAIRness level

fairplus.github.io/Data-Maturity

join

FAIR: experiences from our classrooms and practical guides

for doers, users and contributors

Why FAIR?

Public health crises such as the recent COVID pandemic teach us that efficiently sharing the massive amount of scientific data generated is key to being able to quickly respond to new insights and demand. This calls for guidelines to make data FAIR: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable. Building your new dataset conforming to FAIR principles, or increasing the level of FAIRness of your existing datasets, will lead to a wider sharing of knowledge, greater opportunities for innovation, and more insights that benefit society.

The Cookbook: turning FAIR into practice

The FAIR Cookbook is an online resource for the life sciences that guides researchers and data stewards in their FAIRification journey, and provides policymakers and trainers with practical examples to recommend in their guidance and use in their educational material. The FAIR Cookbook provides over 70 'recipes' for you to learn: how to FAIRify datasets, the levels and indicators of FAIRness, the technologies, the tools and the standards available, as well as the skills required and the challenges to achieve and improve FAIRness.

The Dataset Maturity Model: a path towards improving FAIRness

The starting point as well as endpoint of FAIRification is to assess the current level

of FAIRness of your dataset: the maturity. The Dataset Maturity (DSM) model is intended as a comprehensive reference model for improving FAIRness. The DSM model defines and classifies requirements that constitute an incremental path towards improving the FAIRness level for a research dataset or for an organization. The DSM model is available as a recipe in the FAIR Cookbook.

I want FAIR! Where do I begin?

To start with FAIR, a large collection of online resources is available. Also, the number of data stewards and other experts familiar with FAIR is growing. The FAIRplus website, the FAIR Cookbook, and the DSM website are obvious choices to get started (see back of this flyer). Many examples of FAIRification are available online for free, as well as use cases and testimonies of users that will highlight the possibilities and potential pitfalls. You are also encouraged to contribute to the FAIR Cookbook and help us grow the number of recipes, or assist the FAIR Cookbook team by reporting issues with recipes or pull requests for features. For this, we have a repository on the GitHub software development platform. This is also the place to discuss possibilities and issues with FAIR experts.

Interested? See the back of this flyer for links to resources, the FAIR Cookbook and much more. Join the growing FAIR community today!

